

The Stress-Resiliency of Our Body:

From The Stability of Our Internal Environment, Homeostasis to the Integrative Discovery of Hans Selye About Biologic Stress

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We were the course directors of the 10th International Summer School on Stress: Stress Education, Management & Resilience Training (SEMART), hosted by VIGS (Vienna Institute for Global Studies), Vienna, June 2-6, 2025. Here, we aim to summarize our introductory presentations & emphasize the historical discoveries regarding the stability of the body. Namely, the famous French physiologist Claude Benard ([Claude Bernard biography](#)) recognized in the middle of the 19th century that, despite outside variations in temperature, humidity, etc., our internal body temperature and chemical composition are remarkably stable. The American physiologist Walter Cannon investigated this further in the first part of the 20th century and named this stability "homeostasis". He is also famous for describing the "fight-or-flight" syndrome that he linked to the massive release of catecholamines, especially epinephrine/adrenaline from the medulla of the adrenal glands. These neurotransmitters are rapidly degraded in our body and remain effective for only a few minutes. Hans Selye (Nature, 1936, 1950) recognized the seminal role of the adrenal cortex from which glucocorticoids are released during the alarm reaction, this "general adaptation syndrome" that he named later stress response. As opposed to the short lived-catecholamines, the steroid hormones remain active in our body for 3-4 hrs and are responsible for the morphologic triad of stress response.

The first publication of Hans Selye on stress response (1936) & his subsequent descriptions of 3 stages of biologic stress

The 3 stages of stress response:

- 1. Alarm reaction:**
 - Massive release of adrenaline
 - Increased cortisol levels
- 2. Stage of resistance:**
 - Markedly increased cortisol secretion
- 3. Exhaustion**
 - Decreased cortisol level
 - Adrenocortical exhaustion

The "triad of stress":

- Adrenal hyperemia & hypertrophy
- Gastroduodenal ulcers (hemorrhagic erosions)
- Thymolympathic atrophy

The organ-specific contribution of Hans Selye in the development of stress concept

Hans Selye's concept of "cross-resistance" describes how our bodies not only return to baseline after stress but can also achieve improved states of adaptation. Later, it transformed into stress

resilience. It explains why people who navigate challenges skillfully often emerge stronger than they were before distress occurred. Physiological resilience is a term used to describe an individual's capacity to mobilize the body's adaptive potential in response to stress thresholds. Among various factors that shape its state are age, pre-existing health conditions, metabolic status, lifestyle choices, physical activity, sleep quality, nutrition, and acclimatization to cold or heat exposure.

High physiological resilience elevates the threshold at which stressors cause discomfort and harm, whereas low resilience increases vulnerability to the same stressors. Since personal metabolic status is crucial for developing physiological resilience, its predictive determinants can be used to understand the body's stress resilience.

Every individual has a unique "**Stress resilience signature**," which refers to how the body responds to and recovers from different types of stressors. This signature includes:

Autonomic Responsiveness: How quickly and intensely the sympathetic nervous system activates, and how efficiently the parasympathetic system initiates recovery.

Hormonal Patterns: Cortisol rhythm, insulin sensitivity, and thyroid function all influence how process stress and build resilience.

Metabolic Flexibility: The ability to switch between different energy sources and maintain stable blood sugar under varying metabolic demands: postprandial (after meal) based on insulin, glucagon, incretin hormones (GLP-1, GIP), gastrin, adrenaline/epinephrine, leptin, ghrelin, circadian (e.g., growth hormone or melatonin), or ultradian (e.g. glucocorticoids) or diurnal rhythms (e.g. uncoupling protein 1 (UCP1) from brown fat).

Inflammatory Response: How the immune system reacts to stressors and how quickly inflammation resolves.

Understanding the body's physiological resilience enables the design of personalized protocols that help maintain metabolic health. The "Three Pillars of Physiological Resilience" include:

Pillar 1: Responsive Activation - capacity to mount an appropriate stress response when challenges arise. It refers to the optimal functioning of an individual's hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, sympathetic nervous system, and metabolic systems.

Pillar 2: Efficient Recovery – our ability to baseline and initiate repair processes after stress exposure. It depends heavily on parasympathetic function, sleep quality, and nutritional status.

Pillar 3: Adaptive Growth – the capacity to use stress exposure to build greater future capacity. It involves neuroplasticity, metabolic flexibility, and the development of what Selye called "cross-resistance."

The presented concept of physiological resilience as an integrative system of mobilization adaptive potential represents a promising target for addressing metabolic alterations, helping to

understand the modern view on different subtypes of obesity and its comorbidities. Interesting Danish research on increased brown fat deposits, even in a sub-Arctic climate, supports the notion that Selye's words, "stress can make you stronger," can be applied to understanding the contribution of physiological resilience to metabolic health through the brown-white fat dynamic.

In summary, although the stability of the body started to be understood in the middle of the 19th century, it was expanded by the recognition of "fight-or-flight" syndrome linked to the massive release of short half-life catecholamines (epinephrine, norepinephrine). Subsequently, Hans Selye established the foundation of more complex adaptation syndrome (later named biologic stress) which included the crucial role of corticosteroid hormones released from the adrenal cortex. He later recognized that short exposure to distress made the body more resistant to severe distress. This "cross resistance" led to the modern concepts of stress resilience.

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